

may be assumed to hold valid and the equation (1) reduces to

$$V_t = \frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = 2k_1 K [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) clearly explains first order kinetics with respect to the substrate and hydroxide ions at their low concentrations as observed experimentally. Direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(VIII) oxide is also clear. At higher concentrations of the substrate and hydroxide ions the reverse inequality

$$k_2 \ll [\text{OH}^-] \{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [\text{OH}^-] + k_1 K [\text{S}] + k_{-1}\}$$

will hold good and in this case equation (1) reduces to

$$V_t = -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 K [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{S}]}{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [\text{OH}^-] + k_1 K [\text{S}] + k_{-1}} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) clearly explains zero order kinetics with respect to the substrate at its higher concentrations. It also explains retardation due to OH^- ions at higher alkali concentrations. Direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(VIII) oxide even upto its many fold variation in concentration is also explained by this equation.

Further validity of the rate law might be made by plotting $1/V_t$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/[\text{S}]$. The straight lines with positive intercepts at $1/V_t$ axes clearly indicate the validity of the rate law (1) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. (A, B) Plots of $1/(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{comp}]$ (Table 3); (C, D) plots of $1/(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 4); (A, C) propan-1-ol, and (B, D) butan-1-ol.

The k_2 values calculated from the intercepts of $1/V_t$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ plots (Figs 1A and B) come out to be 1.21×10^{-3} and 1.45×10^{-3} for propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol, respectively. Again from the slopes of

$1/V_t$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$, the values of $K_1 k$ (where, $K_1 = k_{-1}/k_1$) come out to be 51.65 and 82.64 for propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol, respectively (Figs. 1C and D). The values calculated from different methods also verify the validity of rate law (1) and the proposed mechanism.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of some 4-Piperidones by Cerium(IV)

K. SELVARAJ, S. SANKARAN and B. PREMA

Department of Chemistry, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore-641 014

and

K. RAMARAJAN*

Department of Chemistry, C. B. M. College, Coimbatore-641 042

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THE Use of Ce^{IV} as an oxidant has been the subject of several publications¹⁻⁷. However, to our knowledge, no systematic investigation of the kinetics of oxidation of 4-piperidones by Ce^{IV} has been carried out. The present study is an attempt in this direction.

Experimental

The piperidones used in the present study were prepared by literature procedures^{8,9}. Acetic acid (AnalaR) was refluxed over CrO₃ and distilled. Other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

All the kinetic runs were made under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping the substrate and acid concentrations always in large excess over that of Ce^{IV}. The ionic strengths of the reaction mixtures were kept constant by the addition of Na₂SO₄. The rate was followed by withdrawing aliquots (2 ml) of the reaction mixture at suitable intervals, pouring into a known excess (5 ml) of standard Fe^{II} solution and titrating the unused Fe^{II} against standard dichromate. All the reactions were followed for nearly 60% conversion of the oxidant and the results were observed to be reproducible within ± 3% deviation. The bromination kinetics were followed under pseudo-zero order conditions by holding the substrate concentration in large excess over that of bromine.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing a known excess of the oxidant Ce^{IV} to react with the substrate in presence of H₂SO₄ in aqueous 50% acetic acid medium and estimating the unreacted Ce^{IV}. The stoichiometry was found to be in the mole ratio of 2 : 1 for oxidant to substrate.

Product analysis: A mixture of piperidone (0.025 mol) and Ce^{IV} (0.020 mol) was allowed to react in aqueous acetic acid (50%, v/v) in presence of sulphuric acid (0.1 M). The reaction mixture was neutralised with ammonia, extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml) and the combined ether extract evaporated. The oily liquid obtained was tested for the presence of 1,2-diketone by treating with hydroxylamine hydrochloride, alkali and Ni^{II}. Only piperidones 1 and 6 gave a positive test (development of red colour) indirectly confirming the introduction of OH group at the alkyl substituted α-carbon atom during oxidation.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of six variously substituted *N*-methyl-4-piperidones (1–6) by Ce^{IV} were investigated in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid at 303 K.

- 1; R¹ = H, R² = H, R³ = H
- 2; R¹ = CH₃, R² = H, R³ = H
- 3; R¹ = C₂H₅, R² = H, R³ = H
- 4; R¹ = *n*-C₄H₉, R² = H, R³ = H
- 5; R¹ = CH₃, R² = CH₃, R³ = H
- 6; R¹ = CH₃, R² = H, R³ = CH₃

The data presented in Table 1 confirm the first order dependence of the rate on the substrate concentration. Under the conditions (Table 1), the

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON CONCENTRATION OF *r*-2, *cis*-6-DIPHENYL-*trans*-3 METHYL-*N*-METHYL-4-PIPERIDONE (2)^a

[Ce^{IV}] = 0.002 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.100 M,
Solvent = AcOH – H₂O (1 : 1, v/v). Temp. = 303 K.

[S] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
20.0	42.1	21.1
29.9	64.0	21.4
39.9	80.0	20.1
50.1	110.0	22.0

Mean = 21.1 ± 0.82

^ak₁ = k_s K [piperidone] and k₂ = k₁/[piperidone].

values of 10³ k₂ (M⁻¹ s⁻¹) for substrates 1–6 are respectively 22.3, 21.1, 39.5, 32.9, 3.51 and 8.80. Variation of [H₂O⁺] over the range 0.100–0.500 M did not result in any appreciable change in the rate constant for *r*-2, *cis*-6-diphenyl-*trans*-3-methyl-*N*-methyl-4-piperidone (2). This confirms the independence of rate on [H₂O⁺].

Under the conditions [Ce^{IV}] = 0.002 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.100 M and [substrate] = 0.020 M in aqueous 50% (v/v) acetic acid at 303 K, the values of 10³ k₂ (M⁻¹ s⁻¹) for 10² [Na₂SO₄] = 2.00, 4.75, 7.50, 10.0 and 15.0 M are respectively 8.91, 13.3, 17.3, 23.2 and 33.9. Thus, the rate increases linearly with the increase in ionic strength of the medium in accordance with the relation (1)¹¹,

$$\ln k = \ln k_0 + (b_A + b_B - b_{\pm}) \mu \quad (1)$$

This suggests the involvement of either two neutral molecules or a neutral molecule and an ion in the rate-limiting step of the reaction.

Although a change in the polarity of the medium does not have much of an influence on the rate of the reaction, the values of 10³ k₂ (M⁻¹ s⁻¹) in 40, 50, 60 and aqueous 70% (v/v) acetic acid are respectively 3.51, 3.25, 2.66 and 2.16 under the conditions : [Ce^{IV}] = 0.002 M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.100 M and [substrate] = 0.020 M at 303 K—a small but consistent decrease in the rate with decrease in polarity of the medium points to an activated complex more polar than the reactants (in the slow step). This result can be understood by means of the participation of two neutral species in the rate-limiting step of the reaction.

Mechanism and rate law: Although ceric ion is capable of forming a number of complexes in H₂SO₄, for concentrations of H₂SO₄ upto 2 M Ce(SO₄)₂ and HCe(SO₄)₂ are believed to exist¹². As the present investigation is carried out at [H₂SO₄] = 0.100 M, Ce(SO₄)₂ may be assumed to be the

reactive species. Both the ionic strength effect and the medium polarity effect are in favour of such a neutral oxidant species.

The observation that the enolisation rates (as measured by bromination rates) are always smaller than those of oxidation, excludes the involvement of an enol intermediate in the mechanism of oxidation. Besides, a (Michaelis – Menten) plot of $1/[S]$ vs $1/k_1$ passes through the origin, which indicates the formation of a loose complex between piperidone and Ce^{IV} . A similar observation was made previously in the case of oxidation of cyclohexanone with Ce^{IV} . Finally, the introduction of acrylamide into the reaction mixture results in its polymerisation. All these observations have prompted us to propose a free radical mechanism for the oxidation (Scheme 1). The rate law for the mechanism follows equation (2).

Scheme 1

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = k_s K [\text{piperidone}] [Ce^{IV}] \quad (2)$$

Structure and reactivity: Although in the case of piperidones 2–4 a choice exists as to the nature of the α -hydroxyketone product (1 and 5 are symmetrical and 6 can form only one type of α -hydroxyketone), the fact that the final product contains the hydroxy group on the alkyl substituted carbon atom (as evidenced by product analysis) suggests the preferential abstraction of H-atom from the alkyl bearing α -carbon atom. The reactivity of piperidones stand in the order, $3 > 4 > 2 \sim 1 > 6 > 5$. We can group the piperidones into two categories–5 and 6, with low reactivity, constitute one group and the rest the other. The low reactivity of 5 and 6 may be attributed to steric hindrance from the alkyl substituents for the formation of the complex between piperidone and Ce^{IV} species (small K).

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Effect of Radiation on Phenobarbitone Sodium and Tetraphenobarbitone Cupratosodium in Methanolic Medium

H. JIMENEZ*

Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Valencia, Spain

and

M. DOLZ, R. BELDA and J. V. HERRAEZ

Department of Physics, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Valencia, Spain

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THE study of the effect of uv radiation on barbituric derivatives in aqueous medium has recently been done. Some of the products of degradation have been identified by comparison with hydrolysis processes, and the influence of various parameters in the reactions^{1,12,18,19} has been investigated. If the uv radiation falls in a methanolic solution containing Cu^{II} ion, redox dynamic reversible processes yield in solution the $Cu^{II} - Cu^I$ and the $CH_2OH - CH_2O$ ^{3,4,6,11,15,16,17,19}.

In view of the interest of the photochemical processes in medicinal substances and its contribution to the knowledge of allergens, we have studied the incidence of uv light on the complexes synthesised^{8,9} with barbituric ligands sensitive to uv light. The present research consists of the study of the photochemical degradation of the ligand (phenobarbital sodium) in a methanolic medium and the complex Na_2CuL_4 , to observe the processes that are taking place and also the formation of new compounds of Cu^I produced in the redox reactions with the intermediate degraded products of the ligand.